

NIGERIA AND INSECURITY: THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF INTERNAL CHARACTERISTICS AND CAUSAL FACTORS

Aniefiok Esetang¹

Anietie J. Atai²

¹National Open University, Abuja

²dopseabasiibom@yahoo.com

Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

ABSTRACT

Insecurity, resulting from kidnapping, banditry, terrorism and secession killing of IPOB in the South Eastern among others has not only become a source of anxiety for residents of Nigeria for over 13 years now but has also attracted world negative attention to Nigeria. Many scholars and policy makers propagating their opinions on the issue tend to concentrate their blame on the economic weakness of the country as the causative factor. The objective of this theoretical paper is to show that insecurity in Nigeria is a multi-causative phenomenon emanating from systemic deficiency in the areas of Nigeria's geography, politics, socio-economy, military, religion, world technology and external influences and not merely from the economic weakness of Nigeria as popularly presented. Extrapolating the analytical and explanatory tool of interstate warfare and using documentary source of information, the paper argues that state's national attributes such as type of government, size of the territory, its ideology, geographical location, its population dynamics, resource wealth and economic performance, military capabilities, citizens' level of educational attainment and its leader's personality determine whether a state is susceptible to insecurity, and other factors like geographical, socio-economic, military, and religious factors are contributory to insecurity in Nigeria. The researchers therefore recommend that multi-pronged solution strategies be adopted to reposition the military, the economy and politics/governance of Nigeria to end the insecurity crises.

KEYWORDS

Insecurity, internal characteristics, causal factors, and Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

During the era of military rule in Nigeria, high incidence of armed robbery, the major form of insecurity at that time, was regarded as the by-product of the Nigerian civil war and military regimentation of the society as they made arms and ammunitions available to unauthorized persons. Based on this notion, Nigerians became tired of continued military governance and looked forward to civilian rule which, according to them, would reduce tension and bring about a secured society. Unfortunately, the ushering in of civilian government in 1999 coincided with the onset of globalization, information superhighway, internet, laptops, global system of mobile communication (GSM) and TV cable news (Imobighe, 2007). The world became a global village where events in the remotest corner of the world were heard and watched almost instantly everywhere in the world either through laptops or smart phones. Violent ways aggrieved people in other parts of the world react to unresolved discontents and grievances in their societies became imbibed by Nigerians. The nature of insecurity in Nigeria thereby became varied and more deadly (Mboho and tahirih, 2014). Owing to receding geo-political boundaries and revolution in electronic transfer of money that also became operational at that time, it was no longer difficult for criminally-minded elements and marginal groups to procure weapons or acquire the technical know-how to build lethal improvised weapons for use to prosecute terrorism in Nigeria. Today, insecurity has assumed alarming dimension and are perpetrated in diverse forms such as banditry, armed robbery and kidnapping. Others are river piracy, farmers-herders killings, communal boundary clashes, Boko Haram terrorism, secessionist killings from IPOB among others (Udoh *et al.*, 2020)

From the early episodes of kidnapping of oil workers by Niger Delta militants from Rivers and Bayelsa States in the early 2000 and Boko Haram suicide bombing campaigns from 2009, insecurity peaked in 2015 resulting in the control of a total of 26 local government areas in three states of the North-East region; fourteen, seven and five in Borno, Adamawa and Yobe States respectively (Odeniyi, 2022). Their violent campaign later spread to other states such as Zamfara, Nasarawa, Kaduna, Kano, Plateau, Niger and Sokoto States as well as the Abuja Federal Capital Territory where they attacked government installations, worship centres, recreational areas, motor parks and other densely populated areas (Odeniyi, 2022).

No state escaped from this orgy of violence. Indeed, insecurity rendered the transportation sector of the economy (road, rail, marine and even air transportation) unsafe for commuters. According to the Agora Policy study report titled, “Understanding and Tackling Insecurity in Nigeria” conducted by Armed Conflict Location and Events Data Project, Boko Haram and the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) both carried out not less than 1,480 attacks in different parts of Nigeria between July 2009 and August 2022.

These resulted in the death of about 15,111 victims and the displacement of 3.2 million Nigerians (Odeniyi, 2022). Is it valid, as Imobighe (2007) has alluded to, that Nigeria is now in the “age of terrorism”? This article is focused on analysing the internal state's characteristics and other causal factors contributing to insecurity in Nigeria.

THEORETICAL EXPLORATION

Stephen Walt, a political scientist once asserted that “we need theories to make sense of the blizzard of information that bombard us daily. Everyone uses theories - whether he or she knows it or not” (in Kegley and Blanton, 2011). Theories play the role of a map or frame of references that makes the completely puzzling world around us intelligible.

How can we explain insecurity in Nigeria? Why do people or group engage in organised violence against their state or fellow human being? Scholars and policy makers have put forward various explanations or causes of violence. Summarising these explanation as it concerns inter-state wars Kegley and Blanton (2011) grouped them into three levels of analysis:

1. Aggressive traits inherent in human nature
2. Detrimental national attributes that makes some states likely to engage in aggression, and
3. Global volatile conditions that encourage disputes to be militarised.

These analytic categories can be extrapolated down to individual and intra-state levels since states are constituted by people and groups such that their possible violent instinct can determine whether states should initiate war or not. Similarly, detrimental national attributes first impinge on citizens thus helping to influence the socio-economic and even political character of the state. Lastly, volatile global system also affect citizens' disposition towards peace or violence. Let us now appraise these levels of analysis one by one.

STATE'S INTERNAL CHARACTERISTICS

A state's national attributes such as type of government, size of the territory, its ideology, geographical location, its population dynamics, resource wealth and economic performance, military capabilities, citizens' level of educational attainment and it leader's personality determine whether a state is susceptible to insecurity or not. Let us discuss them one by one.

- **The Type of Government**

Between authoritarian government and democracy which of them is more permissive and vulnerable to insecurity? According to Vasconcelos (2005) authoritarian government is more vulnerable to insecurity. He argues that democracies possess more effective weapons to

fight terrorism than to authoritarian regimes. He identified these weapons as respect for basic freedom and due process. On the other hand, advocates of authoritarian government's approach are of the view that since extremist elements exploit democratic freedom to commit their crimes, so preventing the abuse of freedom requires curtailing the freedom scope of all citizens. The weakness of this approach, according to Vasconcelos, is that repression of civilians and their non-differentiation between civilians and killers provides extremists with fertile recruiting conditions by discrediting the government in the eyes of a significant part of its population. This enhances extremists' status as the champions of causes of the oppressed people which does not actually reflect their true goals. According to him, democracies have the advantage of having effective intelligence services that are subject to public scrutiny and accountability. This oversight mechanism serve to limit abuses of power as well as punishing top officials that fail to do their jobs properly. He asserts that democracy only fails to stem insecurity when it abandons its ethics and falls into authoritarian temptation and therefore becoming weak and vulnerable to armed attack. He recommended that democracies should first and foremost strengthen their intelligence agencies so that they can detect and dismantle terrorist cells while respecting basic rights and due process, and secondly, ensure greater coordination and synergy among security agencies of the state.

This framework of analysis is very useful in understanding why insecurity in Nigeria actually worsened at the advent of democracy from 1999 to date whereas it was better during the authoritarian era of the military. It is either our democratic administrations abandoned ethics of democracy or its intelligence services were weak and uncoordinated. We will therefore use this theory to analyse and explain insecurity in Nigeria.

- **The Geographical Size of the Country**

Is there any relationship between the size of the country and its susceptibility to insecurity? In other words, is a geographically large country more prone to internal insecurity than smaller country? Characteristically giant states are bound to have diversity of cultural groups (Rodee *et al*, 1976). To achieve stability and security such states may resort to ruling their heterogeneous subjects through strong and central bureaucratic control. When this control is weak, due to internal decay among other factors, armed revolt is likely to occur as it was in Soviet Union, the largest country in the world, through the Bolshevik revolution of 1917 and the collapse of Soviet Union in 1991. It can also be used to explain the breakup of Sudan, the largest African country, into new Sudan and South Sudan in 2011. The theory cannot however account for the endurance of China, the second largest country in the world, despite its ethnic/cultural diversity and giant land mass.

Does this theory support the endurance of Nigeria or does it explain insecurity currently facing Nigeria? Empirical evidence will answer these questions.

- **Ideology**

States where the spirit of nationalism is very strong within the nationalities constituting the state instead of to the entire country, there is the high likelihood of arm revolt (Rourke and Boyer, 1998). The “ethnic cleansing” frenzy in the Bosnia-Herzegovina and other former Yugoslav republics is a case. Similarly, states where realism is the principle guiding their leadership and the general population, cases of violent crackdown of dissension and opposition groups is likely to be very high (Jackson and Sorensen, 2003) Example is in Zimbabwe under Mugabe. Furthermore, advocates of feminist ideology underscore the power of women in using their relationships to negotiate and maintain peace. To them, the route to peace is to avoid violence, discrimination and inequality against women. According to Melander (2005) where cultural norms condone the mistreatment of women and deny them opportunities for education and employment, the likelihood of civil war will be high.

Is ideology analytically useful in explaining insecurity in Nigeria? Does Nigeria has officially approved ideology? It can be argued that Nigeria adopts Welfarism as its ideology base on Section 14(2) (b) of the 1999 Constitution as amended which stipulates that “the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government...” However, the actual economic policy pursuits of various civilian administrations since the advent of the Fourth Republic in 1999 to date which was/is neo-liberalism have been/are diametrically opposite of welfarism. Thus while welfarism prescribes that government should control economic affairs of the state and provide range of free services to the people who need them such as medical care, unemployment benefits, free education, care for the aged among others, neo-liberalism, on the other hand, prescribes minimum government control and more private sector activities in the economy. For example, the removal of subsidy on petroleum products by some past civilians administrations and by the present Tinubu administration is a neo-liberal policy.

- **Geographical Location and Physical Features**

Can a country's geographical location in relation to other countries as well as its physical features be significant in determining its vulnerability to insecurity? The answer is yes. Record shows that the more a country is isolated from other countries geographically, the more its security is enhanced. Britain and United States separated by oceans are example. These two countries have escaped major inter-state wars of the last century due to their protection by ocean (Rourke and Boyer, 1998). Conversely, a country with long border with other countries is likely to be highly unsecured especially if it has no protective topography such as mountains, rivers and plains. Such country is prone to constant cross border infiltration by armed groups. Mali, Burkina Faso and DR Congo are good example of this

scenario. Nigeria is also a good example of favourable location for terrorism. According to Fadipe (2003) the centralized location of Nigeria is attractive target for extremist groups from other West African countries because from it they can launch attacks anywhere on African continent within hours. He argued that the centralised position can also serve as a central point of assembly in attracting criminal gangs not only from Nigeria but also throughout Africa.

In view of the points put forward above, this factor of geographical location of Nigeria will be very useful in explaining insecurity in Nigeria.

- **Population Dynamics**

Demographic factors affect security. A country with a large population of young people (youth bulge) especially males who are out of school, out of work and charged with hatred have a higher probability of experiencing outbreak of violent insurrection. Similarly, having a large proportion of adult less than 30 years of age without jobs is an invitation to violent confrontation. According to Kegley and Blanton (2011) when youths and young adults face poor economic conditions and lack resources to provide for their families, they turn to religious fundamentalism to counter their frustration and despair resulting in armed religious extremism.

Population dynamics is central and indeed a very strong factor in explaining insecurity in Nigeria. Apart from high population growth (206 million in 2020), Nigeria has the highest youth population in the world. According to Akinyemi and Mobolaji (2022), 70% of Nigeria's population is under 30 years of age while 42% is under the age of 15 years. The neo-liberal economic policies pursued by various civilian administrations since 1999 have not favoured youth employment. According to Oyesola (2008) their policies have destroyed jobs and created unemployment. That explains the rise in unproductive ventures such as crime during the period. It is also the reason why insecurity has become worst also. This factor will illuminate our understanding of the insecurity challenge in Nigeria.

- **Resource Wealth and Economic Performance**

A country's resource wealth can be both a blessing and a curse. A country that derives enormous wealth from its resources without ensuring that its benefit trickles down to the masses is in serious security danger. Communities can regard their resources as a curse if the benefits of such exploited natural resources are either denied them or not adequately compensated to them. According to Kegley and Blanton (2011) armed revolt is likely to be the reaction of people who feel that they are unfairly deprived of their wealth and status that they rightly deserve in comparison with advantages of others. This appears to explain Niger Delta militancy in the South-South in early 2000s and banditry in the north in places where solid minerals are mined. Similarly, if the economy of the state is performing well but the benefits

are not felt by the less privilege, it can create a wide gap between people's expectations of what they deserve and what they are provided with. Since poverty is a strong motivator for allegiance, armed gangs could exploit poverty among the people to attract them to their criminal groups by promising them security and improved standard of living. According to Justino (2009), the poorer a people are at the stage of conflict, the higher the probability of their participating and supporting armed terrorists. This factor is very useful in explaining insecurity in Nigeria.

- **Military Capability**

Military strength and capabilities including intelligence capability can curb insecurity. However, they alone may not always prevent internal revolt and insurrection as for example Irish Republic Army (IRA) in Britain. It is grievances and complaints over one issue or the other that eventually snow-balls into insecurity. It is unwise to employ military force to quell all protests or grievances since it can escalate it. Peaceful suasion can douse tension. Blanton (1999) observes that over the past decades, developing countries have been among the biggest customers in the robust global trade in arms and have built huge armies to guard against potential aggression and to control their own citizens. That has not prevented conflicts in these countries. Low military capability may not holistically explain incidence of security challenges facing many developing countries. Other factors may come into play. Why did Nigeria, as a military power in the West African sub-region, not quickly wipe out insurgency for over 13 years (2009 - 2022)? This is what we intend to investigate in this study.

- **Leader's Personality**

A leader's personality, the images of reality he holds and the kind of action he takes is decisive in either controlling or escalating grievances into open confrontation. Leaders who subscribe to constructivist theory leverage on the current circulating ideas in the area about material conditions shared by the people of the area to determine whether to take action on a challenge or not. A leader's reaction in the face of insecurity is based on how his administration views the challenge. Kegley and Blanton (2011) show a typical example. According to them, British nuclear weapons are less threatening to the United States than the same nuclear weapons held by North Korea. This is because shared Anglo-American expectations about one another differs from those between United States and North Korea. In other words, the collective image/idea about the damage which insecurity can wrought on the nation may encourage or discourage a leader's action. Did Nigerian religious groups think that religious extremism by Boko Haram is useful or harmful to Nigeria's society?

- **Citizens' Level of Educational Attainment**

Advocates of liberalism argue that conflicts and insurrection are caused by adverse

conditions experienced by citizens in their daily lives (Jackson and Sorensen, 2003). One of such adverse conditions is the non-availability of education to all. Education expose citizens to new and modern ideas, mold their attitudes, behaviour and thinking in positive direction. It also equip them to assume higher roles in the society (Mazrui, 1978). Countries where citizens suffer from low level of educational attainment are fertile grounds for recruitment of rebel group (Ukeje, 2003). Although other factors may intervene to promote insecurity, however, low educational attainment among inhabitants is important factor. It is therefore not unexpected that insurgency began in educationally disadvantaged northern zones.

- **Volatile Global System**

Interdependent world system enables a country's insecurity affliction to be fuel by external factors. The more external factors are involves the more fierce, long lasting and difficult it would be to solve it. Proponents of neo-realist theory explain that intra-state war spring from changes in the global system which is characterise by decentralised sovereign states and absence of overarching authority to which all states and non-state actors like terrorists are subject to. According to Imobighe (2007), globalisation together with Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has improved global reach of aggrieved groups across the world. The recent innovations in miniaturisation of weapons of war which makes it easy for small arms and light weapons to proliferate and be smuggled across national borders undetected; the emergence of internet that ensures that knowledge of science and technology relating to the making of explosives and other weapons of mass destruction are learned online by criminal groups and the development of electronic banking system which has facilitated their easy access to funds from abroad have enabled criminal gangs to exploit loose global environment to equip themselves well for terrorism. That is why it has been difficult for them to be easily defeated.

In our theoretical exploration in this section, we have appraised explanations advanced by scholars and policy makers on why some people take up arms against the state and fellowmen. We have shown theoretical foundations driving these explanations at the level of man's nature, the internal state's attributes and global factors. We have identified their strengths and weaknesses as it pertains to Nigeria's situation. We will leverage on these strengths in explaining the scourge of insecurity in Nigeria.

CAUSES OF INSECURITY IN NIGERIA

Insecurity in Nigeria is a multiple causative factor problem. In order to make the causes more comprehensible, it would be necessary to group them into identical factors as shown hereinafter.

Geographical Factors

Included as these factors are the size and diversity of Nigeria; the centralised location of Nigeria; its porous border, and climate change/desertification of savannah regions of Nigeria.

The land mass of Nigeria is the second in Africa with an area of 941,849 sq. km. Its greatest length (east-west) is about 1,046 km. It also has a 960km long coastline bordering the Atlantic Ocean (Opadiran, 1989). The enormous size present a big problem to security forces in terms of effective security control. The multi-lingual, multi-ethnic and multi-religious composition of Nigeria has robbed Nigerians from speaking with one voice and uniting to confront criminal gangs harassing Nigerians. This disunity can best be exemplified by how ethnic-religious bias influenced the views and actions of key office holders of the Buhari administration on herdsmen terrorist killings in Benue State. Thus, while the then Inspector General of Police, Ibrahim Idris argued that it was a mere communal misunderstanding, his Defence Minister counterpart, Mansur Dan-Ali blamed it on the blocking of grazing route (Omatseya, 2018). Also, the centralised location of Nigeria in the African continent and its porous border did facilitate the upsurge of insecurity. While the location is attractive assembly centre and launching point for terrorists from other regions of Africa (Fadipe, 2003), its porous border enhanced their free inflow and outflow from Nigeria. In 2011, for example, the Nigerian troops arrested 8 mercenaries from Chad and Niger republics in Benue State (Emmanuel, 2011). In 2016, Nigerian soldiers similarly captured 40 back up foreign fighters when Camp Zero and Camp Shape headquarters of the Boko Haram at Sambisa forest were captured by the military (Alli, 2016). Lastly climate change/desertification of the Sahel and Savannah regions of West Africa have been blamed for cross border migration of killer armed herdsmen of other countries into Nigeria. These foreign armed herdsmen were blamed for insecurity in the farming belt of north-central zone of Nigeria. According to Leo Ogor, a former Minority Leader in the House of Representatives, “The effects of climate change such as accelerating desertification of grazing land and lower rainfall has heightened herdsmen's southwards push into fertile farmlands, thereby generating increasing possibilities of farmers/herdsmen conflicts that now accounts for more deaths than the Boko Haram insurgency...” (Anofi, 2018).

Political Factors

The enthronement of democracy; inciting/intemperate utterances of some sectional leaders; arming of thugs for electioneering campaigns; weak leadership personality/absence of political will; politicisation of security issues and controversy over term of office of the president all caused insecurity in Nigeria.

Does democracy escalate or subdue insecurity? The case of Nigeria appears to show that it actually promotes insecurity. For example, when the military held sway insecurity was minimal. Grievances expressed by groups such as Movement for the Survival of Ogoni People (MOSOP) of Ken Saro Wiwa and Movement for the Actualisation of Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB) of Ralph Uwazuruike were pursued peacefully. However, when democracy was enthroned from 1999 onward complaints/grievances turned violent. Groups that pursued their agenda violently were Niger Delta Avengers (NDA), Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND). Indigenous Peoples of Biafra (IPOB), Boko Haram, Bandits among others (Esetang and Thompson, 2022). This appears to support the thesis that democracy promotes insecurity. This proposition does not resonate with that of Vasconcelos. According to him, records show that democracies possess more effective weapons to fight insecurity such as the rule of law, guaranteeing of basic freedom and due process than authoritarian military regime (Vasconcelos, 2005). He opined that democracy only becomes vulnerable to insecurity when it abandons its democratic ethics or falls into authoritarian temptation. We postulate that insecurity in Nigeria cannot be validly blamed on abandonment of democratic ethics since it erupted in early 2000s shortly after commencement of democratic rule. It is our view that pent up anger by various groups which could not be ventilated during many years of military authoritarianism suddenly exploded into the open when democratic freedom was enthroned from 1999.

Inciting/intemperate utterances of some sectional leaders instigated insecurity in Nigeria. Mallam Adamu Ciroma was said to have threatened in 2011 that should former president, Jonathan not allow north to retain power in the April election of that year then north would make Nigeria ungovernable. Similar inciting comment was said to have been made by Mohammadu Buhari, the then presidential candidate of Congress for Progressive Change (CPC). He was said to have called on almajiris to lynch anyone who toyed with their votes (Sanusi, 2011). When the result of that April presidential election was won by Jonathan, Boko Haram and Almajiris in the north rioted. They killed innocent corp members working as electoral officers and other people from various regions of Nigeria (Sanusi, 2011).

Arming of thugs for electioneering campaign is another cause of insecurity in Nigeria. According to newspaper editorial, "...desperate politicians intent on winning elections at all cost... recruit and armed private militia that ultimately got out of control (Omosho, 2011). In 2011, top security chiefs of Nigeria resolved to investigate a governor who was alleged to have set up a militant group as a political thuggery enterprise and nurtured it through adequate funding until it metamorphosed into a terror group. The security chiefs also resolved to investigate prominent politicians who held high political offices in the past who were suspected to be funding deadly groups involved in terrorism (Taiwo-Obalonye, 2011).

Weak leadership personality/absence of political will also fostered insecurity in Nigeria. Odere, for example, disclosed that "...Jonathan administration initially vehemently opposed the United States attempt to classify Boko Haram as a Foreign Terrorist Organisation (FTO) which could have mandated the American government to swing into action in tracking the terrorist organisation's source of funding and armaments... It was not until after the abduction of the Chibok girls that Nigerians became aware of several efforts of Britain and the United States to assist the country in fighting terrorism which the Jonathan's administration consistently rebuffed". (Odere, 2014). Similarly, at the inception of terrorism, the ruling administration did not take the threat seriously as they thought it was propaganda of the political opponents. "The standard narrative from government has been to blame incidents of insecurity on political masterminds seeking to gain some partisan capital from the chaos" (Idowu, 2018). This is a good example of how indecision and weak political leadership of the Jonathan's presidency allowed insecurity to become aggravated. This position is supported by Agekameh when he argued that "...bad political leadership has impacted negatively on the performance of the nation's security agencies... successive leadership in Nigeria has not properly discharged its responsibility to ensure efficiency and development of the security services. This may be the reason why our surfeits of security apparatuses, especially the police, cannot cope with crime prevention and law enforcement". (Agekameh, 2010).

Politicisation of security issues has hampered the fight against insecurity in Nigeria. Terrorism is a new form of warfare not previous witnessed in Nigeria. To stem its spread, security expert should be appointed to fight it. Some security heads were appointed on primordial considerations. According to Agekameh "... the top echelon of some... security agencies are outright misfits... Chief of Defence Intelligence (CDI), Gen. Babagana Mongunu was in the Corps of Engineers with no iota of intelligence knowledge before he was drafted to head an outfit where high professional specialisation is required". (Agekameh, 2010). Ironically, this same officer who was rejected by some of his senior military colleagues for allegedly being a misfit in security matters during the Jonathan's administration was subsequently appointed and elevated by the Buhari administration as his National Security Adviser (NSA). The extent to which insecurity worsened under his watch during the Buhari administration is now a common knowledge.

Controversy over term of office of former president, Jonathan also contributed to insecurity in Nigeria. It was on whether former president Goodluck Jonathan should contest the 2011 presidential election or not after he completed the tenure of his late boss president Umaru Yar'Adua. Street riots and killing of innocent people from various regions of Nigeria erupted in some towns in the north following the declaration of Jonathan as the winner of the April 2011 presidential election. Some northern political actors earlier threatened that should

the presidency not be occupied by a northerner they would make Nigeria ungovernable (Sanusi, 2011).

Socio-economic Factors

The socio-economic factors that caused insecurity in Nigeria are: high rate of unemployment among the youths; greed, corruption and indiscipline among Nigerians; unjust access to nation's wealth in favour of the rich and privilege; high illiteracy rate; erosion of traditional values and poor home upbringing of children; heavy drug use by youths; and sponsorship by unpatriotic power seekers.

High unemployment rate among the youths and other Nigerians was the principal cause of insecurity in Nigeria. Nigeria has suffered from high level of unemployment especially among the youths. This has been traced to the ill-digested and poorly implemented policies and programmes of various administrations in Nigeria such as the retrenchment policies under Murtala Mohammed; austerity measures under Shagari; Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) under Babangida; National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS) under Obasanjo, and Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) under Buhari. They brought about retrenchment of workers, withdrawal and hike in prices of social services, hike in unemployment rate and idleness, poverty and inequality among Nigerians. This position is supported by the former governor of Borno State, Kashim Shettima who later became the Vice President of Nigeria. According to him, years of abject poverty, neglect and mass unemployment among the youths in the northern part of Nigeria is the cause of insurgency (Manyam and Oguwale, 2012). According to Ojo (2018), Nigeria is the headquarters of poor people while unemployment moved from about 18% to 23% and as at 2018 was still experiencing worsening poverty and unemployment (Ojo, 2018).

Greed, corruption and indiscipline also enhanced insecurity in Nigeria. Greed is excessive, uncontrolled and burning passion to have more of anything than one really need or deserves (Akinola, NA:5). In other words, it is a rapacious desire to own more and more of just about anything. Greed gives birth to corruption. Corruption occurs when people try to get what they do not deserve by using money, bribes, ethnic connections, religion, family name, threats, harassment among other (Gana, 1989). Corruption is a form of indiscipline. Indiscipline occurs when people exhibit impatience and wanton disregard for rules and regulations or disobey even simple procedures such as lining up in a queue to enter buses or buy petrol among others (Gana, 1987). Corruption is the bedrock of Nigeria's socio-political and economic failures since it distorts government policies and programmes. Perhaps, the most high profile corruption cases which directly hampered the combat of insurgency during the democratic era were Dasukigate Scandal of 2014 and the failed cash for South African arms purchase contract. In 2014 during the administration of former president Goodluck

Jonathan, his National Security Adviser (NSA), Col. Sambo Dasuki (rtd.) diverted N31 billion meant for the purchase of sophisticated weapons to fight Boko Haram and other insurgent groups into private use by sharing it to top members of his ruling political party for 2015 electioneering campaign purposes (Alli, 2015). This became known as Dasukigate Scandal. Similarly, in 2014 during the tenure of the same administrations, \$9.7 million cash purportedly meant for the purchase of weapons was seized by South African Security men as it was being transported into South Africa aboard a private jet by agents of the federal government of Nigeria (Ehikioya, 2015). The weapons were neither purchased nor the cash returned to the government of Nigeria. Revelation of these two corruption cases emerged during the Buhari administration tenure.

The lopsided access to Nigeria's wealth in favour of the rich and privileged and against the poor promoted insecurity. The Nigeria's society does not create equal opportunity for all its citizens. Few privilege people own and enjoy the overwhelming wealth of the country while the poor suffer in penury. Thus, while the rich live in extreme prosperity, the poor glance at them from the gutter with strong inclination to take to crime to survive. According to analyst "Society is inherently unjust and imperfect... (it) demands that everyone must fend for himself in food, clothing and shelter. But because it is imperfect and unjust, society is unable to create enough opportunities for everyone to meet these demands within the confines of legitimacy. Opportunities are circumscribed by tribe, section, religion and other artificialities". (Agbese, 1985). Agbese concludes that the poor not finding opportunities within the law, some seek them outside the law. They commit crimes. The former governor of Borno state and the vice president of Nigeria, Kashim Shettima confirms this fact by arguing that abject poverty, neglect and mass unemployment among the youths in the north was the cause of insurgency in Nigeria (Ogunwale, 2012).

High illiteracy rate in Nigeria also promoted insecurity. Although Boko Haram regards western education as a sin, it is with weapons made through the knowledge gained from western education that they used to perpetrate terror in Nigeria. What an irony! Data from federal ministry of education shows that as at 2021, 31% of Nigeria's population of 200 million was illiterate with the larger percentage coming from the north. That partly explains why religious extremists such as Boko Haram were able to use religion to attract a large number of terror members in the north by brainwashing their illiterate population knowing that they have no capacity of independent thinking and decision owing to their low educational attainment.

Erosion of traditional values and poor home upbringing of children also helped to enhance insecurity in Nigeria. As earlier discussed traditional African society encouraged hard work, honesty and respect for elders and constituted authorities by members. They

frowned at indolence, laziness and criminality. Everybody was his brother's keeper. People who behaved unjustly or involve in theft and violence were severely punished. Colonialism and western education changed all that. People now openly challenge their elders and constituted authority not even peacefully but often violently. Similarly, the costly nature of managing a modern family which necessitates both parents to work and earn income in order to shoulder the heavy burden of their families has deprived their children proper home care and upbringing. Addition to this are increasing cases of broken homes where children are brought up by single parent who may not always be at home to monitor the activities of their children and the friends they keep. It is due to these societal value weaknesses that insurgency have thrived in Nigeria.

Heavy hard drug use by youths and terrorists spurred them up to prosecute terrorism. The military revealed that bandits, Boko Haram and other insurgent groups carry out their murderous campaign against innocent Nigerians under the influence of hard drugs. According to experts, hard drugs such as marijuana, heroin, cocaine among others can, when use, either mobilize the body for action especially prolong activity and take away desire for sleep or reduce nervous activity leading to sleep. (Man's Body, 1976). The former Army spokesman, Col. Sani Usman revealed that military discovered hard drugs, condoms and sex enhancing drugs in camps captured from Boko Haram. According to him "When the military captured their bases and training camps, they never found Quran or other Islamic books, what were mostly found were ammunitions, local charms, condoms and all sorts of hard drugs including sex enhancing ones in their enclaves" (Omotoso, 2015). He also announced the arrest of a supplier of hard drugs and other stimulants to terrorists by 3rd Division troops.

Sponsorship by some unpatriotic power seekers was blamed for continuation of insecurity in Nigeria. There is the allegation that desperate politicians intent on winning elections at all cost recruited and armed private militia that ultimately got out of control (Omotoso, 2011) Allegation of sponsorship was also made by the military. The former acting Director of Army Public Relations, Col. Sani Usman, at the height of terrorist bombings and killings in 2015, accused some prominent elders of Borno State of sabotaging military's efforts in fighting insurrection in their state. In his press statement he warned, "The Nigerian army wishes to inform the public and send a very strong and serious final warning to some prominent individuals and political groups, who hail from Borno State in particular and North East generally... on plans... to undermine and scuttle the fight against terrorism and insurgency in this country" (Omotoso, 2015). Similarly, former government of Kaduna State, Nasir El Rufai, is reported to have in 2016 confessed that he sent emissaries with huge government funds to pay fellow Fulani herdsmen in such countries as Niger, Camerouns, Mali and Senegal for them to stop violence and killings in Southern Kaduna. According to

him, “We got a group of people that were going round trying to trace some of these people in Cameroon, Niger and so on to tell them that there is a new governor who is Fulani like them and has no problem paying compensations for lives lost and... begging them to stop the killing” (Omotoso, 2016). The scheme nonetheless failed and killings in Southern Kaduna became more intense and widespread even up to the end of his administration in 2023. On the other hand, Kolawole thinks differently. He groups all elites as sponsors of terrorism in Nigeria. To him “The real Boko Haram are the big elites in the people, customs, immigrations, civil servants, hungry people who experience biting hunger thereby producing kidnapers, armed robbers, cyber-criminals and prostitutes”. (Kolawole, 2012). He argues that Boko Haram thrives because these people lack patriotism.

Military Factors

The following military factors have been blamed for insecurity in Nigeria. They are: the Nigerian Civil War; weak intelligence capacity of the military and other security agencies as well as rivalry and lack of synergy among them; insubordination of security chiefs to the political authority; the novelty of terrorism warfare to Nigeria's military training; the collusion of some security personnel with criminals in renting out arms to them and lastly lack of modern sophisticated weapons to security agencies. Let us take them one by one.

Nigerian Civil War is the earliest contributor to the mass availability of deadly arms in Nigeria. One of the exponents of this view such as Akinrinade argued that “...escalation and the sophistication of armed robbery can be traced indisputably to the civil war... Guns went into the wrong hands and became a common property... youths... took to the fronts and mastered the use of the weapons of death”. (Akinrinade, 1985). Since then, more sophisticated modern weapons have flowed into Nigeria with occasional interception by security agencies.

Since security agencies are principally responsible for fighting insecurity, many analysts have criticised their weak intelligence capacity, lack of synergy and constant rivalry among them. Two typical cases of their weak intelligence capability are: the United Nations office bombing of 2011 and Dapchi school girls abduction of February 2018. Gregory Starr, the under Secretary in the bombed United Nations office in Abuja, in 2012 disclosed that they received early intelligence report of imminent terror attack on their Abuja office and passed the information in time to the Nigerian government but nothing was done to prevent the attack (Gbadegsin, 2012). In the case of Dapchi school girls abduction, it was learnt that a detachment of the army guarding the school area was withdrawn a few days before the terrorists, dressed in the military camouflage, attacked the school and kidnapped 110 school girls. Before attacking the school, the terrorists moved through town and intelligence report was not transmitted to warn security agencies of the attack even by the police station which is

300 metres from the school (Eriye, 2018). Another weakness noticed was absence of synergy and cooperation among security agencies operating in the war zone. Indeed, this weakness was so open that a foreign observer by name Stephen Davis, an Australian self-confessed hostage negotiator argued that various intelligence units in the war zone were not cooperating with one another in sharing information that could aid quick defeat of the sect (Sanusi, 2014). Instead of cooperation sometimes their rivalry explode into open shoot-out among them resulting in deaths thus attracting newspaper headlines such as “Uneasy calm as Police, Civil Defence Corps engage in bitter rivalry” (Igbonwelundu, 2014). Since they could not work as a team, the security agencies could not quickly defeat insurgency in Nigeria.

The insubordination of security chiefs to the political authority is another factor that weakened the fight against insecurity. The military and indeed all security forces are subordinate to and take directives from political authorities especially as it concerns the focus of that administration. In the combat of insecurity in Nigeria, this was not always the case. The former National Security Adviser (NSA) to former president Buhari, Babagana Monguno is reported to have blamed insecurity in Nigeria on insubordination of security chiefs whom, he alleged, were in the habit of spurning his invitations for meeting in his office. He regretted that security agencies had no respect for his office. According to him, this uncooperative attitude of the security chiefs did hamper his ability to coordinate their operations on the President's behalf. (Idowu, 2018). Also, there were instances where the directives of the President and Commander in Chief concerning security matters were ignored by the military. Similarly, the former governor of Zamfara State, Abdul'aziz Yari disclosed that security forces did not obey the very orders of Mr. President in 2018 at the peak of banditry in his state. The president had ordered that more security personnel be deployed to Zamfara State to fight terrorism. According to him, “Not a single additional security man has reported to the state following the presidential order...” (Idowu, 2018). He regretted that 9 days after the president's order was ignored, terrorists killed more 38 people in Binin-Magaji council area of the state.

The novelty or unfamiliar nature of terrorism warfare to Nigeria's military training is another factor that prolonged insurgency. Although terrorism is as old as human history, the contemporary deadly strain of terrorism world-wide is new. Kegley and Blanton alluded to this phenomenon when he argued, “Previously, terrorism was regarded as political theater, a frightening drama where the perpetrators wanted a lot of people watching, not a lot of people dead. Now there seems to be a desire to kill as many people as possible”. (Kegley and Blanton, 2011). With organization structure of decentralised cells loosely tied together by the internet, email and cellular telephones instead of the usual hierarchical command structures, the warfare becomes unfamiliar to Nigeria's military. The then National Security Adviser (NSA) to former President Goodluck Jonathan, Gen. Oweye Azazi (rtd.) argued that Nigeria was not

responding well and decisively to terrorism because it was not prepared and equipped for such war (Orji, 2011). Moreover, the police whose responsibility is for internal security has suffered from poor training, poor equipment and poor motivation of personnel which made it difficult for them to fight crime (Omotoso, 2010).

The collusion of some security personnel with criminals is another factor that hindered success in the fight against insecurity in Nigeria. After the civil war, some discharged former soldiers refused to surrender their weapons. They instead chose to make brisk business selling them to criminals or used them to perpetrate crime (Akinrinade, 1985). In the Niger Delta area, security agents posted to stem militancy there became sucked in by oil barons who allegedly compromised them with cartons or sacks of hard currency for them to aid and abet them in oil theft or the smuggling of crude oil in the region. According to one analyst, "This is the reason security agents struggle to be posted to the Niger Delta... Occasionally, when you hear the news that badges carrying crude oil illegally are confiscated, it is a mere gimmick. What is simply means is that those involved did not give the security agents enough money to have a freeway" (Agekameh, 2016). Moreover, Omotoso in a newspaper editorial re-echoed "... the allegation that unscrupulous members of some... armed security agencies rent out their arms to criminal elements for pecuniary purposes..." (Omotoso, 2011). This unprofessional conduct has hindered the smooth fight against insecurity.

Lack of modern sophisticated weapons for security agencies is another factor that has hindered the swift defeat of terrorism in Nigeria. Boko Haram was richly equipped by its sponsors with both locally fabricated weapons and sophisticated modern imported ones as evidenced by those captured by the military during operations. To neutralise them, the military has to possess more lethal arsenal. Some examples of items used in building improvised explosive device (IED) discovered by the DSS in a bomb making factory owned by one Malam Abubakar Yola in the Yola suburb of Adamawa State in 2012 were 30 cartons of electric detonator, 22 completed improvised explosive device, synthetic gum, 50kg of ammonium nitrate and 17 safety fuses. Others were 20 raps of phosphorus, six high voltage battery, Q-link motor-cycle remote as well as electric soldering irons. Also discovered were AK47 Magazine, carbide switch light, electrical wire of different sizes among others (Manyam and Ogunwale, 2012). Similarly, an example of imported sophisticated weapons captured by the military from Boko Haram in their failed Maiduguri invasion in 2015 were: Cobra Armoured vehicle, heavy Artillery guns and some machine guns. Others were three Golf cars laden with explosives (Alli and Joel, 2015). Past government's schemes to equip the military with modern weapons suffered various setbacks ranging from corrupt diversion of huge arms purchase funds, for example Dasukigate to meagre release of funds. In 2011 for

example, the then National Security Adviser (NSA) to former President Jonathan, Gen. Owoye Azazi argued that “security agencies need more funds. They get about 10% of what they requested for. They required more funds to order some equipment, especially modern gadgets which would enable them to do most of the things that they are now doing manually” (Alli and Ogunwale, 2011).

Religious Factors

Religious factors such as abetment and non-condemnation of religious extremism by some community/religious leaders as well as ethno-religious bias by ruling leaders at both state and national levels have encouraged and sustained insecurity in Nigeria.

In the case of abetment and non-condemnation of religious extremism by Boko Haram sect at its inception, the Jonathan administration expressed serious concern about the co-existence of the country owing to the silence of northern leaders and elders on Boko Haram terrorist killings. During the tenure of former President Jonathan, northern leaders did not condemn the Islamic sect enough on the spate of attacks and loss of lives and property for over one year. (Taiwo-Obalonye, 2011). This was interpreted by the sect as support for them to continue in their murderous killings.

Also, the continuation and intensity of Boko Haram was enhanced by ethno-religious bias by ruling leadership at the national level. Sustained ethno-religious competition for favour in policy execution has been the bane of various administrations. The handling of captured terrorist fighters was not an exception. Thus, while thousands of innocent farmers in Taraba, Benue and Plateau States among others, mostly of one ethno-religious faith, were killed by terrorists and buried, the terrorists, who were mostly of another ethno-religious faith, were condoned by the ruling leadership or when captured were not prosecuted in court but labeled “repentant terrorists” and made to pass through de-radicalisation scheme and later released. (Omotoso, 2017). In 2023 for example, International Criminal Court (ICC) decried the “wide gap” between arrested Boko Haram suspects and those charged to court and requested the federal government to explain the disparity. It classified insurgency as civil war (Ikhilae, 2013).

Technological Factors

Technological factors such as the invention of global information superhighway, revolution in electronic transfer of funds across borders and online mass media publicity have promoted insecurity in Nigeria. Modern-day terrorism greatly leverage on the tolerant virtual environment of global information superhighway which allows people everywhere to communicate freely without constraints as they watch international cable news in the television and cell phones and use of web to exchange e-mails and join internet chats through

their cell phones, personal computers and billions of fixed line telephones (Kegley and Blanton, 2011). Boko Haram exploit these free communication channels to establish close contact with such deadly terrorist groups like al-Shabab and al-Qaeda in the Islamic Maghreb (AQIM) and to learn new deadly methods of terrorist operations and inspiration. This new global information channels also air horrific images of terrorist operations in other parts of the world to drive fear into the people. Such close collaboration with foreign extremist organisations may have triggered schism in Boko Haram in 2015 following its public pledge of allegiance to Syria based Islamic State (IS) resulting in its radical faction renaming itself as the Islamic State of West African Province (ISWAP) with a new rival leader named to replace long time head, Abubakar Shekau (Feldstein, 2018).

Moreover, this technological revolution also ensured the utilization of information and communication technologies (ICT) and other web based telecommunication technologies to facilitate, and enhance easy transfer of money electronically from one person to another and across border. The use of Point of Sale (POS) through cell phone is a good example of channel used to wire money from abroad to terrorist groups.

Lastly, mass media, both traditional media such as radio and print media especially online media did in some cases, exacerbated insecurity in Nigeria. Since terrorists depend on publicity for survival, they exploit both the traditional media and online media to propagate their extremist ideas and horrific exploits against innocent members of the society. It is argued that terrorist groups generally and Boko Haram in particular depend on the open social media system in democratic countries to further their propagandist goals and messages. One analyst admitted that it is quite effective in gathering attention due to the convenience, affordable and broad reach of social media platforms. According to him, "...when a terrorist attack occurs, social media outlets scramble to break the story. In so doing, they knowingly or unknowingly help to further the agenda of these groups". (Oluwatosin, 2015). He however credited social media with publicising the fight against insurgent groups by the brave men and women of the Nigerian military. A typical example occurred in 2017 when online media published that 30 soldiers were killed by the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS). The Deputy Director of Army Public Relations of the Theatre Command of Operation Lafia Dole, Col. Onyema Nwachukwu dismissed the publication as false. According to him, "...contrary to the report, there was no such attack or ambush on any convoy of troops of operation Lafiya Dole by ISIS, or any other adversary within or outside the theatre of operation" (Olaifa, 2017). Publicity is like oxygen to terrorist groups. If they are denied publicity and funding they quickly decline and die.

Legal Factor

Delay or non-prosecution of captured insurgents is another factor that promoted

insurgency in Nigeria. During the tenure of former president Buhari, a large number of herders arrested by security forces over the herdsmen/farmers killings were never prosecuted in court but were detained perpetually for unknown reasons. According to Saleh Bayari, the National Chairman of Gan Allah - Fulani Development Association of Nigeria, the number of herders detained as at 2019 was about 3,500 (Omotoso, 2019). He argued that not all of them committed the crime but that because all Fulanis were labelled as herders, they were accordingly arrested. The Nation Newspaper editorial called on security agencies involved to fast-track their investigations and charge them to court so that the innocent ones should not suffer unjustly. Therefore, the unwillingness of security forces to take legal action against detained herders and other terrorist groups has not deterred others from committing crime.

External Factors

The external factors that have enhanced insecurity in Nigeria are the free flow of Libyan arms/mercenaries into Nigeria and the ascendancy of global terrorism in early 2000. Arab spring and ECOWAS protocol has been blamed for free flow of sophisticated arms and mercenaries into Nigeria. According to Sale Bayari, “Most of the herdsmen are beneficiaries of the Arab Spring which culminated in Libya where massive small arms and light weapons were obtained” (Alli, 2016). Bayari, who was the National Chairman of Gan Allah-Fulani Development Association of Nigeria further blames ECOWAS protocol on free movement of people into and out of ECOWAS countries without restriction. According to him, this protocol allow foreign Fulani to move freely into Nigeria with their cattle and those attacking them or stopping them from grazing their cattle and those being attacked will not know the difference between the Nigerian herdsmen and the foreign Fulani because they speak the same language and they have the same custom and culture. Former president Buhari similarly blamed Gadafi's gunmen for insecurity in Nigeria (Ojiabor, 2018). Another external factor is the general global ascendancy of terrorism in early 2000s which also affected Nigeria. The upsurge in global terrorism cases as exemplified by the September 11, 2001 World Trade centre bombing in the United States and the London terrorist bombing of July 2005 also influenced the emergence of terrorism in Nigeria. In buttressing this point, Fadipe opined that instability resulting from socio-economic and political turmoil as well as violent clashes that occurred in Nigeria in late 1990s and early 2000s created a conducive environment for global extremist groups to establish their foothold in Nigeria. Thus, while they offered arms, training and funding to Nigerian insurgent groups, the global groups were in turn provided a new base to train their jihadist members for their “holy war” and also a launching pad for attacks both across African region and around the world (Fadipe, 2003). Indeed, the National Commission on Terrorist Attacks Upon United States otherwise known as 9/11 commission, in its report published in 2004, among other recommendations, named regions which United States should closely watch on possibility of emergence or incubation of terrorist groups due to their infiltration. In the West African region, Nigeria was named as one of the two countries to be closely watched. The other one was Mali (Madunagu, 2004).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is clear from the study that insecurity in Nigeria has fundamental

causes which we have variously grouped as issues emanating geographically, politically, socio-economically, militarily, religiously, technologically and externally. That one of these factors, which is weak political leadership/will was decisive in aggravating the level of insecurity in Nigeria. That they failed to combat the menace with the seriousness it deserved until it deteriorated out of control.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the analytical positions of the paper, the researchers make the following recommendations:

1. Multi-pronged approach in combating the menace militarily, socio-economically and politically.
2. Repositioning the leadership of the nation at all levels for national unity and national interest
3. Promoting secularism as stipulated within the codes of the federal constitution for peaceful tolerance of the citizens within the nation's polity
4. Repositioning the various arms and sectors of the nation for national interest and development toward alleviating economic stress among the populace

REFERENCES

- Agbese, D. (1985) "Not an Act of God". *Newswatch*, April 22, pg.10.
- Agekameh, D. (2010) "Nigeria's Security Challenge". *The Nation*, October 20, pg.19.
- Agekameh, D. (2010) "Nigeria's Security Challenge". *The Nation*, October 20, pg.19.
- Agekameh, D. (2016) "Like Boko Haram, Like Avengers". *The Nation*, June 15, pg.19.
- Akinrinade, S. (1985) "Menace of Bandits: Armed Robbers harass Nation and throw fear into the hearts of everyone" *Newswatch* April 22, pg. 12, 17.
- Akinyemi, A. and Mobolaji, J. (2022) "Nigeria's Large Youthful population could be an Asset or a Burden". Retrieved from <http://www.premiumtimesng.com>.
- Alli, Y. (2015) "N31 billion loot: Jonathan Camp to seek talks with Buhari". *The Nation*, December 16, pg.1.
- Alli, Y. (2016) "Army arrest 40 foreigners after Sambisa forest fall". *The Nation*, December 28, pg.8
- Alli, Y. and Joel, D. (2015) "Troops repel Boko Haram attack on Maiduguri" *The Nation*, January 26, pg.4.
- Alli, Y. and Ogunwale, G. (2011) "We Know Police Headquarters Bomber says Ringim". *The Nation*, July 6, pg.2.
- Anofi, D. (2018) "PDP Caucus disappointed over handling of attacks". *The Nation*, January 22, pg.7.
- Blanton, S. (1999) "Instruments of Security or Tools of Repression? Arms imports and Human Rights Conditions in Developing Countries? *Journal of Peace Research*,

36(2).

- Ehikioya, A. (2015) "Buhari to probe Jonathan's \$9.7m failed arms contract". *The Nation*, June 17, pg.1.
- Emmanuel, U. (2011) "Soldiers arrest suspected foreign mercenaries". *The Nation*, June 24, pg.7.
- Eriye, F. (2018) "Dapchi Ordeal: It is a disaster of Incompetence of Service Chiefs who should be fired". *The Nation*, March 4, pg.19.
- Esetang, A. and Thompson, E. (2022) Restructuring and Devolution of Powers: The Imperative for Democracy and Development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advancement in Development Studies* 17(1), 139-149.
- Fadipe, H. (2003) "Nigeria: A breeding ground for Terrorism?" *Punch* July 17, pg.10.
- Fadipe, H. (2003) "Nigeria: A breeding ground for Terrorism?" *Punch* July 17, pg.10.
- Feldstein, S. (2018) "Do Terrorist Trends in Africa Justify the US Military Expansion?" <http://carnegieendowment.org>.
- Gana, J. (1989) Political Education Manual. Abuja: MAMSER.
- Gbadegsin, S. (2012) "Slouching towards Hade: An Update". *The Nation*, June 22, pg.64.
- Idowu, K. R. (2018) "Security Suck". *The Nation*, July 9, pg.17.
- Igbonwelundu, P. (2014) "Uneasy calm as Police, Civil Defence Corps engage in bitter rivalry" *The Nation*, September 6, pg.14.
- Ikhilae, E. (2013) "Boko Haram: ICC queries gap in arrest, prosecution". *The Nation*, November 25, pg.53.
- Imobighe, A. (2007) Bridging the Artificial (Divide: Achieving Global Peace in an Age of Terrorism. *Nigerian Journal of International Affairs*, 33(2).
- Jackson, R. and Sorensen, G. (2003) *Introduction To International Relations: Theories and Approaches*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Justino, P. (2009) Poverty and Violent Conflict: A Micro-Level Perspective on the causes and Duration of Warfare. *Journal of Peace Research* 46(3).
- Kegley, C. and Blanton, S. (2011) *World Politics: Trend and Transformation*. Boston: Wadsworth, pg.247.
- Kolawole, E. (2012) "Containing the many facets of Boko Haram: The Nation, August 15, pg.20. Madunagu, E. (2004) "What happened on September II?". *The Guardian*, September 9, pg.65.
- Mazrui, A. (1978) *Political Values and the Educated Class in Africa*. London: Heinmann Educational Books Ltd.
- Melander, E. (2005) Gender Equality and Interstate Armed Conflict. *International Studies Quarterly*, 49, December. Vasconcelos, A. (2005) "Fighting Terrorism

- Democratically”. *Punch*, August 6, pg.16.
- Mboho, K. S. and Tahirih, E. U. (2014). An appraisal on the role of the Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps in the reduction of Vandalism of Oil Pipelines in the Niger Delta Region. *Journal of Environment and Earth Science*. Vol.4, No. 18.ISSN 2224-32 16 (Paper) ISSN 2225-0948 (Online). www.iiste.org. **U.S.A.**pg 53-61.
- Odeniyi, S. (2022) “ISWAP killed 15, III persons in 1,480 attacks - Report”. *Punch*, November 7, pg.18.
- Odere, F. (2014) “Boko Haram: Decoding Alexander Nekrassor”. *The Nation*, July 31, pg.70.
- Ogunwale, G. (2012) “Boko Haram bomb factory discovered in Adamawa”. *The Nation*, April 18, pg.8.
- Ojiabor, O. (2018) “Row over Buhari's link of killer-herdsmen to Gadaffi”. *The Nation*, April 13, pg.1.
- Ojo, J. (2018) “Nigerian Politics, economy and security in 2018”. *Punch*, December 26, pg.22.
- Olaifa, B. (2017) “No soldier killed by ISIS, says Army”. *The Nation*, October 11, pg.43.
- Oluwatosin, O. (2015) “Role of Social Media in war against insurgency”. *The Nation*, October, 29, pg.27.
- Omatseya, S. (2018) “Camouflage of Carnage”. *The Nation*, February 12, pg.48.
- Omotoso, G. (2010) “Still On Security”. *The Nation*, June 23, pg. 13.
- Omotoso, G. (2015) “Troops find hard drugs in Boko Haram Camps”. *The Nation*, September 9, pg.60.
- Omotoso, G. (2016) “Paying the enemy”. *The Nation*, December 8, pg.15.
- Omotoso, G. (2017) “43 Repentant Insurgents for De-radicalisation”. *The Nation*, July 24, pg.40.
- Omotoso, G. (2019) “Divisive Rhetoric”. *The Nation*, July 28, p.g.13.
- Opadiran, J. (1989) “The Nigerian Environment”. Abuja: Unpublished Manual of Readings for Social Mobilisation Officers (SMOs) MAMSER.
- Orji, N. (2011) “Jonathan and Security Challenges”. *Daily Sun*, November, 21, pg.15.
- Oyesola, B. (2008) “Improving the Quality of Life in Nigeria”. *Daily Sun*, April 12.
- Rodee, Anderson et al (1976) *Introduction To Political Science*. Tokyo: Mc Graw-Hill.
- Rouke, J. and Boyer, M. (1998) *World Politics, International Politics on the World Stage*. Dushkin: Mc Graw-Hill.
- Sanusi, M. (2014) “Jonathan and Harambombers”. *The Nation*, June 24, pg.22.
- Taiwo-Obalonye, J. (2011) “North's Silence is Sabotage - FG”, *The Sun*, Sanusi, M. (2011) “Jonathan and Harambombers”. *The Nation*, June 24, pg.22.
- Udoh, E. R., Mboho, K. S., and Umo, U. E. (2020). Government and the Management of Security Challenges in Nigeria: A Study selected Local Government Areas in Akwa Ibom State North West Senatorial District. *AKSU Journal of Social and Management*

Sciences (AJSMS), Nigeria. Vol. 3, No. 1, ISSN: 2504-933X, pp. 95-108.

Ukeje, C. (2003) "Sierra Leone: The Descent into Civil War". In Sesay, A. *Civil Wars, Child Soldiers and Post-conflict Peace Building in West Africa*. AESTRAGE, College Press Publishers Ltd.